

VAKA TAKDİMİ

CASE REPORT

A RARE CAUSE OF ABDOMINAL PAIN: VAGINAL FOREIGN BODY

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ABSTRACT

Abdominal pain is a symptom that is the most common reason for admission to the emergency department and for which anamnesis is important in differential diagnosis. Vaginal foreign bodies, one of the causes of abdominal pain, can occur with various symptoms in women of all ages. Vaginal foreign bodies can be used to provide sexual stimulation, birth control, curettage, to prevent uterine prolapse, in cases of harassment and to hide illegal substances. Vaginal foreign bodies may vary depending on age groups. Tampons, condoms, menstrual cups, and items used for sexual satisfaction are common in adults. Although they are diagnosed by anamnesis, they can also be noticed through gynecological examination or imaging studies. In our case, a 43-year-old female patient applied to our emergency department with abdominal pain. The patient was alcoholic and anamnesis could not be taken. In the examinations, there was a foreign body image on the standing direct abdominal radiography. The patient underwent a rectovaginal examination. The patient, whose vaginal external examination revealed a foreign body, was consulted with a gynecologist and obstetrician. He was taken into emergency surgery. The foreign body was removed during the operation. Complications that may occur due to foreign objects remaining in the vagina are of clinical importance. These complications may include infection, ulceration, bleeding and fistula. Vaginal objects should be kept in mind in case of abdominal pain and additional symptoms in female patients of all ages who apply to the emergency department.

Key Words: Abdominal pain, foreign body, vagina

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INTRODUCTION

Abdominal pain is one of the most common symptoms that cause admission to the emergency room. There are many causes of abdominal pain, which makes differential diagnosis difficult. Anamnesis is of great importance in differential diagnosis. Vaginal foreign bodies, one of the causes of abdominal pain, is a clinical condition that may occur with various symptoms in women of all ages, and it is not always possible to take anamnesis (1). One of the reasons that make taking anamnesis difficult is the patient's feeling of shame and desire to hide it.

Vaginal foreign bodies are encountered more frequently in children in the literature, but they can also be seen in adults for various reasons (1). These reasons are mostly; for sexual stimulation, for birth control, for curettage, to prevent uterine prolapse, in cases of harassment and for storing illegal substances (2). Vaginal foreign bodies may vary depending on age groups. While toys and household items are common in the pediatric age group, tampons, condoms, menstrual cups and items used for sexual satisfaction are common in adults (3).

Symptoms may vary across age groups. In adults, discharge, bleeding, and abdominal pain may occur. These symptoms have a wide differential diagnosis.

Although intravaginal foreign bodies are diagnosed by anamnesis, they can also be noticed by gynecological examination or imaging studies in cases where the anamnesis is insufficient (4).

CASE REPORT

In our case, a 43-year-old female patient applied to our emergency department with abdominal pain. The patient was alcoholic and anamnesis could not be taken. Laboratory tests and standing direct abdominal radiography were requested from the patient. In laboratory tests, the pregnancy test was negative and other parameters were within the reference range, and there was no pathological value. There was a foreign body image in the X-ray taken (picture 1), but a pelvis X-ray was also taken for the full image. A foreign body-glass (picture 2) was also seen on the pelvic radiograph. The patient underwent a rectovaginal examination. The patient, whose vaginal external examination revealed a foreign body, was consulted with a gynecologist and obstetrician. He was taken into emergency surgery. The foreign body was removed during the operation (picture 3). During the operation, no bladder or rectum injuries were observed, which can be seen in such cases, but there was serious injury to the side wall of the vagina (6).

Picture 1: Standing direct abdominal radiography, the entire foreign body is not visible.

Picture 2: Pelvic radiography, foreign body – glass

Picture 3. Foreign object removed during the operation (glass)

DISCUSSION

Vaginal objects should be kept in mind in the presence of abdominal pain and additional symptoms in female patients of all ages who apply to the emergency department (1).

Complications that may occur due to foreign objects remaining in the vagina are of clinical importance. These complications may include infection, ulceration, bleeding and fistula (3)(5).

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